

A CASE REPORT ON ACUTE CHEST SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

Acute Chest Syndrome (ACS) is a life-threatening pulmonary complication and a leading cause of hospitalization and mortality in patients with sickle cell disease (SCD). It is characterized by new pulmonary infiltrates on imaging alongside clinical features such as fever, chest pain, cough, dyspnea, and respiratory distress. This report explores the clinical presentation, pathogenesis, risk factors, and emerging therapies of ACS in patients with SCD, with particular emphasis on the role of nitric oxide (NO) in pulmonary vascular regulation. The pathophysiology of ACS is complex and multifactorial, involving infection, fat embolism, pulmonary infarction, hypoventilation, and inflammation—often triggered by vaso-occlusive crises or asthma. Risk factors include younger age, low fetal hemoglobin levels, prior ACS episodes, and asthma. A key mechanism involves sickling of red blood cells in the pulmonary microvasculature, leading to hypoxia, inflammation, and impaired gas exchange. Anemia

and hemolysis further disrupt nitric oxide (NO) metabolism and impair hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction (HPV), contributing to ventilation-perfusion mismatch. Early recognition and aggressive supportive care are crucial to prevent progression and mortality. Diagnostic investigations include chest X-ray, full blood counts, renal and liver function tests, arterial blood gases, sputum culture and sensitivity etc. Treatment focuses on oxygen therapy to

maintain saturations above 96%, pain control, empiric antibiotics, hydration, and blood transfusion when indicated. Pain management must balance efficacy with the risk of hypoventilation, and patient-controlled analgesia (PCA) is preferred over continuous opioid infusions or NSAIDs leads to side effects. Inhaled NO has demonstrated potential to temporarily improve oxygenation and reduce pulmonary pressures, though clinical evidence. Antimicrobials, particularly macrolides and cephalosporins, are recommended empirically. Advanced therapies like high-frequency oscillatory ventilation, hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, and chronic transfusions may be required in severe or recurrent cases. Management focuses on early recognition and supportive care, including oxygen therapy, patient-controlled analgesia, antibiotics, hydration, and blood transfusions. Preventive and adjunctive therapies—such as exchange transfusions, incentive spirometry, and emerging agents like NO donors, L-arginine, and bronchodilators—may reduce morbidity and recurrence. Further research is needed to validate the therapeutic role of inhaled NO and optimize treatment strategies for ACS in SCD.

KEYWORDS: Acute chest syndrome (ACS), Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), fetal haemoglobin (HB f), patient controlled analgesia (PCA), Nitric oxide (NO), Sickle cell anemia(ACS).

INTRODUCTION

Acute chest syndrome (ACS) is a frequent respiratory complication of sickle cell disease (SCD). The acute chest syndrome is a defined has acute pulmonary illness in a patient with sickle cell disease. ACS is also defined as a new pulmonary infiltrate and some combination of fever, chest pain, and signs and symptoms of pulmonary diseases such as tachypnea, cough, and tightness of chest and shortness of breath. The acute chest syndrome definition is vague because there are many causes of ACS, and its pathogenesis is complex and not thoroughly understood (1). ACS is a leading cause of death with sickle cell disease and it is important as early recognition and symptomatic treatment will reduce morbidity and mortality (2). The multiple lobe involvement and recurrent infiltrates are common in ACS with SCD, and the duration of clinical illness and radiologic clearing of infiltrates are prolonged to 10–12 d. ACS with CSD is a frequent cause of hospitalization for patients. approximately 25% of deaths in patients ACS with SCD. In the Cooperative Study which shows that Sickle Cell Disease, the death rate in patients with ACS was 1.1% in children and 4.3% in adults. In recent study reports that ACS mortality of <1% for children up to 9yr of

age, 2% for children aged 10–19yr, and 9% for adults (1). The key to managing ACS is awareness, anticipation of its development, particularly in high-risk patients, and timely intervention with specific treatments such as oxygen and blood transfusion (2). The recent study of nitric oxide (NO) biology, suggesting that hemoglobin binds NO and regulates local pulmonary NO concentration and delivery of NO to the micro vascular system. The nitric oxide may offer a possibility of new therapy for ACS with CSD. The effects of NO on sickle cell hemoglobin and the microvasculature will be detailed. And the interactions of NO with hemoglobin to regulate hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction and ventilation/ perfusion matching will be presented.^[5]

SYMPTOMS OF ACS: chest symptoms such as

- Dyspnea
- Chest pain
- Fever with chills
- Tightness in chest
- Cough
- Breathing very fast
- Tachypnea
- Wheezing^[4]

AETIOLOGY: Acute chest syndrome (ACS) has many causes, including pulmonary infections, fat Embolism or blood clots in the lungs, shallow breathing, asthma and problems with the nitric oxide pathway. These triggers because red blood cells to sickle, stick to blood vessels, break apart, and block blood flow, leading to poor oxygen exchange in the lungs. This results in the symptoms of ACS. In adults, ACS usually happens after a pain crisis (VOC), and in children, about half of ACS cases also follow a pain crisis.^[6]

RISK FACTOR FOR DEVELOPMENT OF ACS INCLUDES

Nearly half of all patients with sickle cell disease can experience at least one episode of ACS, with some having multiple episodes. About half of ACS cause develops during hospitalization for another complication, usually a vaso-occlusive crisis. Other important triggers are general anesthesia, surgery and asthma related bronchospasm. While the exact cause is often unknown, pulmonary infarction and infection are believed to be key contribution. The following risk factors are:

- Age
- Hematologic factor (low steady state HbF%)
- Genotype and haplotype
- HLA type
- Past history of ACS
- Smoking
- Asthma and airway hyper- responsiveness
- Surgery and anesthesia
- Seasonal variation
- Chronic hypoxia
- Infection
- Pregnancy
- Rib infarction
- Sedation with opiate analgesia
- Recent/ current painful crisis
- Genetic polymorphisms in nitric oxide metabolism

PATHOGENESIS: The acute chest syndrome with sickle cell disease has a varied pathogenesis that includes infection, occlusion of the pulmonary vascular bed by sickle erythrocytes, marrow fat, and lung infarction. ACS is a common clinical manifestation of many pathologic processes that may coexist, and establishing a specific cause is often difficult.^[1]

PATHOGENESIS OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE: Sickle cell anemia is a genetic disease affect the African Americans. Approximately 0.15% of African American children are homozygous for the sickle cell gene, and 8% have sickle cell trait. This autosomal recessive disorder is characterized by a single amino acid substitution (glutamic acid to valine) in the beta subunits of the hemoglobin tetrameric protein. Upon deoxygenation, hemoglobin S undergoes conformational changes that expose a hydrophobic region surrounding the valine moiety in the beta-subunit. Polymerization with other hemoglobin tetramers occurs with the formation of long polymer chains that ultimately distort the erythrocyte membrane.^[5]

The molecules of Hemoglobin S are aggregate upon deoxygenation to form polymer nuclei that become the seeds for further polymerization. In sickle red cells, hemoglobin S

polymerizes as the cells traverse the microvasculature. Factors that increase the intracellular concentration of haemoglobin (red blood cell dehydration), that increase time spent in the microcirculation (increased expression of adhesion molecules), or deoxygenation of hemoglobin, all contribute to increased polymerization. Increased levels of non-S hemoglobins such as fetal hemoglobin (haemoglobin F) or haemoglobin A2 slow the rate of polymerization and reduce intracellular polymer content at any oxygen saturation. As polymer content increases, the red cell becomes increasingly rigid, retarding transit through the microvasculature. The severity of sickle cell disease has been described by models that emphasize either the intracellular kinetics of polymer formation (and cell sickling) or the extent of polymerization and cell rigidity at the reduced oxygen saturation values of the various tissues and organs.^[5]

The pathogenesis of sickle cell anemia can also be affected by adhesion of the sickle erythrocytes to the microvascular endothelium. And increased expression of adhesion molecules on erythrocytes and endothelial cells, interaction with leukocytes, increased levels of circulating inflammatory cytokines, enhanced microvascular thrombosis, and endothelial rupture are all thought to contribute to obstruction of the arterioles by polymer-containing sickle erythrocytes.^[5]

PATHOGENESIS OF ACUTE CHEST SYNDROME: Acute chest syndrome (ACS) is a pulmonary illness with sickle cell disease is a common complication and reason for hospital admission in patients with sickle cell disease (SCD). It is also the most common cause of death in this patient population. Most of the time, the trigger for ACS in an individual patient cannot be identified. However, although infection is the most common identifiable cause for ACS, other important triggers are vaso-occlusive crisis (VOC) and asthma.^[5]

The ACS second most common cause of hospitalization in persons with sickle cell anemia and accounts for 25% of premature deaths. The prospective Cooperative Study of Sickle Cell Disease observed in 3,751 subjects with sickle cell anemia. In that 29% incidence of ACS over a 2-yr period. This translates into an attack rate of 12.8 episodes/100 patient years for homozygous sickle cell disease. ACS rates vary directly with steady-state leukocyte counts, hemoglobin concentration, and, inversely proportional with age and hemoglobin F level.^[5]

The Current understanding of the pathophysiology of adult ACS is limited but suggests that ACS may be a specific form of acute lung injury which can lead to progress to the acute

respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). This injury is caused by multiple exogenous insults or triggers superimposed upon the genetic based pathophysiology. These insults are believed to involve “sludging of blood” in the pulmonary microvasculature secondary to erythrocytes with high polymer content, and resulting infarction of the pulmonary parenchyma, as well as possible bone marrow fatty embolization from infarcted bone, microvasculature in situ thrombosis, macrovascular pulmonary embolism, and infection table. The reader is referred to recent reviews for further discussion of this hypothesized pathophysiology. It should be noted that pulmonary involvement may contribute to further hypoxemia and subsequent intracellular hemoglobin S polymerization, thus causing a “vicious cycle.”^[5]

The Cooperative Study on Sickle Cell Disease and collected data on 1,722 ACS episodes. The Patients with ACS presented with fever (80%), cough (74%), chest pain (57%), dyspnea (28%), productive cough (24%), hypoxia (mean PaO₂ of 71 mm Hg), leukocytosis, and infiltrates on chest radiographs, and they often progressed to multilobar pulmonary disease indistinguishable from the acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS).^[5]

In this study adults, children are more likely to have fever, cough, upper and middle lobe infiltrates on chest radiograph, and to present in the winter months. Adults more commonly experience chest pain and shortness of breath, with fever and cough only occurring in approximately 60% of cases. Indeed, 50% of adults experience the pain of VOC prior to developing ACS, whereas only 11% of children have an antecedent crisis. Adults present with lower lobe disease and more frequently develop multilobe involvement (36 versus 24% of children) and pleural effusion (21 versus 3%). Although bacterial infection is more common in children (3.5 versus 1.8%), the severity of illness is greater for adults. Adults receive more frequent transfusions (39 versus 22%), are hospitalized longer (9 versus 5.4 d), and suffer a higher mortality (4.3 versus 1.1%).^[5]

The differences in acute chest syndrome may be due to age-dependent etiologies. The seasonal peak, increased rate of bacteremia, and milder course observed in children may reflect an infectious etiology, whereas the lower lobe predominance, frequent pain, lower rate of bacteremia, and severe course observed in adults may be attributable to bony infarction and atelectasis of the lower lobes, pulmonary thrombosis and infarction, and/or fat embolism as the precipitating causes in this group.^[5]

THE ROLE OF NITRIC OXIDE AND HEMOGLOBIN IN HYPOXIC PULMONARY VASOCONSTRICTION: THE IMPACT OF ACUTE CHEST SYNDROME

The 93rd amino acid of cysteine on the beta-hemoglobin chain has recently been identified that nitric oxide binds to hemoglobins heme moiety, with a potential binding site on beta chain. In fact that heme has an affinity for NO that is 3,000 times that of oxygen. Heme iron forms a planar structure encircled by four nitrogen atoms in the center of a protoporphyrin ring. A histidine residue binds from below, leaving a sixth site available for binding oxygen, carbon monoxide, NO, and other ligands. NO is rapidly taken out of solution by oxyhemoglobin and converted to nitrate after the oxidation of ferrous iron to ferric (met-hemoglobin). In vitro and in vivo hemoglobin serves as a biologic sink for NO. Recent data suggest that this NO-binding property of hemoglobin may play a vital role in physiologic NO balance in the lungs. Indeed, hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction depends on the rapid clearance of airway and alveolar-derived NO by hemoglobin. We will now summarize recent studies describing the role of NO in hypoxic vasoconstriction, the role of hemoglobin in this process, and conclude with a hypothesis about how anemia, NO and a failure of hypoxic vasoconstriction may conspire to produce the acute chest syndrome.^[5]

NITRIC OXIDE AND HYPOXIC VASOCONSTRICTION

The lungs need a balance between air reaching them (ventilation) and blood flow (perfusion) to keep oxygen and carbon dioxide levels stable. Oxygen levels in the alveoli mediate local vascular tone to achieve this balance. A fascinating picture is emerging that NO affects these oxygen-mediated changes in perfusion. The lung contains all three nitric oxide synthase enzymes (NOSs): type I or neuronal NOS, type II or inducible NOS, and type III or endothelial NOS. Types I and III NOS are expressed constitutively, regulated by intracellular calcium concentrations and produce picomolar levels of NO, whereas type II NOS is induced and produces nanomolar levels of NO, independent of calcium concentration. The production of NO by these enzyme systems regulates hypoxic vasoconstriction as well as the drop in pulmonary vascular resistance observed at birth. In fact, adenovirus-mediated transfer of the type III NOS gene into rat lungs reduces acute hypoxic vasoconstriction and in fetal animal lungs, type III NOS expression is induced by oxygenation and ventilation, reducing pulmonary vascular resistance. Selective inhibition of type II NOS has also been shown to increase pulmonary vascular resistance by 70 to 80%.^[5]

In recent study of Dweik and colleagues in humans that type II NOS activity is regulated by oxygen concentrations in the physiologic range. NO levels measured at the mouth of 11 subjects during oral breathing (to diminish nasal NOS contribution) correlated directly with FIO₂ in the hypoxic range. Subjects breathing 0.15 FIO₂ exhaled approximately 10 to 20 parts per billion (ppb) NO, whereas subjects breathing 0.05 FIO₂ exhaled 1 to 5 ppb NO. The investigators then examined NOS II enzyme kinetics in vitro under varying oxygen concentrations and in the presence of excess substrate (L-arginine, NADPH, FAD, FMN, and tetrahydrobiopterin). Again, in vitro NOS II production of NO directly correlated with oxygen concentration. These findings suggest that oxygen, in the physiologic range, is the rate-limiting substrate for NO synthesis, and this may be the mechanism coupling oxygen, NO, and vascular tone to maintain an equal ventilation/ perfusion ratio.^[5]

HEMOGLOBIN, NITRIC OXIDE AND HYPOXIC VASOCONSTRICTION

Studies in isolated, perfused animal lungs have shown that red blood cells are important for normal hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction (HPV). Deem and colleagues found that this effect depends on hematocrit level (the amount of red blood cells) and is likely due to hemoglobin's ability to bind and remove nitric oxide (NO). In their study, ventilated rabbit lungs were tested with hematocrit levels of 30%, 10%, and 0%. They measured exhaled NO, NO_x, and pulmonary artery pressure during both normal oxygen (21% O₂) and low oxygen (5% O₂) ventilation. As expected, under low oxygen, exhaled NO decreased and pulmonary artery pressure increased. However, in anemic animals (with low or no hematocrit), exhaled NO was higher and pulmonary artery pressure was lower—indicating weaker HPV. When NOS (nitric oxide synthase) was blocked using L-NAME, NO levels returned to normal in the anemic animals and HPV was restored in the 0% hematocrit group. There was no effect in the normal (30%) group. These results suggest that anemia weakens HPV by increasing NO levels.^[5]

Studies by Dweik and colleagues support that this process also happens in humans. They measured nitric oxide (NO) in the airways during a bronchoscopy. At first, NO levels were higher (5 to 10 parts per billion), but during exhalation, they dropped to 0 to 1 ppb. The low NO levels toward the end of exhalation likely come from the alveoli, suggesting that NO production in the alveoli is balanced by how much is taken up by hemoglobin and broken down locally.^[5]

Anemia can affect how well the lungs work. It disrupts how the body uses nitric oxide (NO) and how blood vessels respond to low oxygen, leading to problems with matching air flow and blood flow in the lungs. This causes conditions like pneumonia, ARDS, and acute chest syndrome in sickle cell anemia to worsen. In earlier studies, researchers found that when rabbits had anemia (but normal blood volume), their lungs exchanged gases poorly. Anemia increased blood flow to parts of the lung that weren't working well (collapsed areas), which led to more blood passing through the lungs without picking up oxygen.

HEMOGLOBIN, NITRIC OXIDE, HYPOXIC VASOCONSTRICTION AND THE ACUTE CHEST SYNDROME

These mechanisms may be important in acute chest syndrome (ACS) in sickle cell anemia. Almost all patients with ACS are anemic, with average hemoglobin levels around 7.8 g/dL, and many continue to break down red blood cells during the illness, losing about 1.6 g/dL more. Even a small problem with hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction (HPV) can reduce oxygen levels in the blood, which increases the chance of hemoglobin S forming harmful polymers. This can cause more red cell sickling, more hemolysis, worse anemia, and even less oxygen delivery—creating a cycle that may damage small blood vessels and organs. Some case studies show that blood transfusions can quickly improve oxygen levels and patient outcomes in ACS. One study measured oxygen in the blood before and after transfusion in 27 ACS patients. On average, oxygen levels rose from 65 mm Hg to 86 mm Hg within 12 to 24 hours after transfusion. Restoring HPV may have helped improve oxygenation in these patients.^[5]

Several studies have shown a clear link between hemoglobin levels and oxygen saturation. Rackoff and colleagues found that as hemoglobin levels dropped, oxygen saturation measured by pulse oximetry also dropped. However, this was due to changes in how oxygen binds to hemoglobin, not because there was less oxygen in the blood (PaO₂), which they didn't measure directly.^[5]

In studies where PaO₂ was measured directly, patients with anemia often had low oxygen levels, averaging about 85 mm Hg. The difference between the oxygen in the lungs and the blood (called the AaPO₂) increased as hemoglobin levels dropped. When hemoglobin was around 6–7 g/dL, the difference was 25–40 mm Hg, but when hemoglobin was 11 g/dL, the difference was smaller (5–20 mm Hg).^[5]

When patients breathed 100% oxygen for 20 minutes, calculated shunt levels (blood bypassing the lungs) ranged from 4% to 19%. These results may be due to the heart pumping more blood in response to anemia, causing more blood to bypass the lungs. Another theory is that anemia causes nitric oxide (NO) to build up in the lungs, widening blood vessels and increasing the shunt.^[5]

Figure 1: Pulmonary NO production is regulated by oxygen concentration in the physiologic range. Reductions in oxygen concentration result in reductions in NO production and hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction. However, reductions in NO are dependent on active scavenging of NO by hemoglobin. Severe reductions in red blood cells (RBC) and hemoglobin result in increased local NO levels despite reduced NO production, and loss of hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction.

INHALED NITRIC OXIDE AND ACUTE CHEST SYNDROME

Inhaled nitric oxide (NO) has recently been considered as a possible treatment for acute chest syndrome (ACS), but there is very little data on how it affects the condition. So far, only a few individual case reports suggest that NO might help improve oxygen levels and shorten the duration of ACS.^[5]

In one report, Atz and Wessel described how two children with ACS who were on ventilators improved after inhaling 80 parts per million (ppm) of NO for 15 minutes. Their oxygen levels (PaO₂) increased from 69 and 107 mm Hg to 176 and 185 mm Hg. One child's heart pressure dropped from 60 to 40 mm Hg, and the other's dropped from 41 to 26 mm Hg. That second child also had a better heart output, with no change in pressure inside the lungs. These improvements lasted, and NO was stopped after 92 and 47 hours.^[5]

Even though the patients improved, it's unclear if NO was the reason, since they also received other treatments like fluids, blood transfusions, and oxygen. Studies of inhaled NO in patients with ARDS show that although NO improves oxygen levels at first, the control group (not receiving NO) usually catches up within 1 to 4 days. Also, NO has not been shown to reduce how long patients need ventilators or improve survival. So, more careful studies are needed to understand its true effect.^[5]

Observed the effect of nitric oxide (NO) on oxygen levels is thought to work by improving the matching of ventilation (airflow) and blood flow in the lungs. Even temporary improvements in this balance can help increase oxygen in the blood and reduce the sickling of red blood cells in the lungs and other parts of the body. The acute chest syndrome in sickle cell anemia might be a type of lung problem where brief improvements in oxygenation can significantly affect recovery. However, there are some important things to keep in mind. Some patients who receive inhaled NO for conditions like ARDS may experience worsened oxygen levels and high blood pressure in the lungs once the treatment stops, possibly due to the body producing less NO on its own. This means that while patients may improve with NO treatment, they might relapse after stopping the treatment. Currently, the main treatments for acute chest syndrome include hydration, oxygen therapy, antibiotics, exchange transfusions, and incentive spirometry. The use of inhaled NO is still experimental and cannot be recommended until more clinical trials confirm its effectiveness.^[5]

Figure 2: The “vicious cycle” of vaso-occlusive crisis on the acute chest syndrome in sickle cell disease. Regional tissue hypoxia and other factors lead to hemoglobin S polymerization (*) and formation of polymer fibers () in sickle erythrocytes. Erythrocyte rigidity and sickling results in microvasculature occlusion, tissue infarction, and erythrocyte hemolysis. Anemia leads to a reduction in NO binding by red cells. Local pulmonary NO accumulation impairs hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction such that insults that lead to lung injury (the acute chest syndrome) are manifested by worsened shunt physiology and hemoglobin desaturation. The anemic patient with acute chest syndrome suffers a two-pronged attack: loss of pulmonary NO scavenging (with loss of hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction) and loss of peripheral NO delivery (with loss of peripheral vasodilation).**

INVESTIGATION

- Chest x-ray
- Full blood count
- Biochemistry

- Electrolytes
- Renal function test
- Liver function test
- Serology
- Atrial blood gas (ABG)
- Blood and sputum cultures
- Nasopharyngeal viral swabs
- Oxygen therapy (>96% of oxygen saturation)

Mekontso Dessap and colleagues found that high levels of B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP), cardiac troponin I (cTnI), liver enzymes (aminotransferases), and direct bilirubin were linked to higher tricuspid regurgitant velocity (TRV) in severe acute chest syndrome (ACS). TRV is used to assess pulmonary pressure, and 60% of patients with severe ACS had elevated pulmonary pressure, often only during the ACS episode.^[1]

Secretory phospholipase A2 (sPLA2) is an inflammatory molecule that is usually low in blood but rises in conditions like sepsis and ACS. It breaks down phospholipids into fatty acids, which can harm the lungs. sPLA2 levels are much higher in sickle cell disease (SCD) patients with ACS than in those without. Increased sPLA2 levels can predict ACS 24-48 hours before it's diagnosed. C-reactive protein (CRP) also rises in line with sPLA2, and both can help predict ACS during a vaso-occlusive crisis in SCD patients.^[1]

MARKERS USED

- B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP)
- Cardiac troponin I (cTnI)
- Aminotransferases (liver enzymes)
- Direct bilirubin
- Tricuspid regurgitant velocity (TRV)
- Secretory phospholipase A2 (sPLA2)
- C-reactive protein (CRP)

TREATMENT: In early detection and supportive treatment may limit its severity and prevent death. Treatment includes continuous pulse oximetry and delivery of supplemental oxygen to patients with hypoxemia, adequate pain management, empiric antimicrobial

therapy, monitoring the hematologic parameters, blood transfusion, and maintenance of good hydration.^[1]

PAIN MANAGEMENT: Pain management is important to prevent shallow breathing. To control pain, opioids are often used, but they can cause harder and worsen (lungs) breathing problems and may worsen lung issues. Pleuritic chest pain, which causes sharp pain when breathing, is a concern because it can lead to shallow breathing and lung collapse. NSAIDs (pain relievers like ibuprofen, diclofenac, aceclofenac etc.) should be avoided in patients with acute chest syndrome, which may cause worsening the symptoms.^[1]

An intercostal nerve block using has a long-acting local anesthetic like bupivacaine can help relieve chest wall pain and make breathing easier. It also reduces the need for strong pain medicines, which can cause breathing problems like low saturation of oxygen or lung collapse. The nerve block can last 18–24 hours and can be repeated if needed. Once pain is well controlled, patient should start exercise (warmup).^[1]

Too much fluid (over hydration) and too many opioids should be avoided because they can make Acute Chest Syndrome (ACS) worse. Mechanical ventilation may be needed for patients with severe disease and acute respiratory distress syndrome. The use of patient-controlled analgesia (PCA) helps to minimize over sedation and hypoventilation but still provides adequate pain control. In a small randomized controlled study, the efficacy of intravenous morphine administration with PCA was compared with continuous infusion (CI) of morphine in patients with SCD during vaso-occlusive crisis. Twenty-five consecutive episodes of vaso-occlusive crisis in 19 patients with SCD were included in the study. Patients in the PCA group had a markedly and significant lower mean and cumulative morphine consumption when compared with the patients in the CI group (0.5 mg/h vs. 2.4 mg/h ($P < 0.001$) and 33 mg vs. 260 mg ($P = 0.018$), respectively). The mean daily pain scores were comparable (4.9 vs. 5.3). The lower mean and cumulative morphine consumption in the PCA group led to significant less nausea and constipation during treatment when compared with the CI group. Furthermore, a non-significant 3-d reduction in the duration of hospitalization was observed in the PCA group. PCA results in adequate pain relief at much lower doses of morphine administration.^[1]

BLOOD TRANSFUSION

Blood transfusions can help prevent and treat Acute Chest Syndrome (ACS) by increasing the amount of oxygen blood. Although there isn't a lot of strong evidence, doctors have seen that transfusions can be helpful, so they should be considered early in the illness.^[6]

A simple transfusion (adding blood) may be needed if a patient has low oxygen levels—especially if their oxygen saturation (SpO₂) is below 90% or if their haemoglobin (Hb) levels have dropped from their normal baseline.^[6]

An exchange transfusion (replacing some of the patient's blood with donor blood) might be used if oxygen levels are low but Hb is still above 9.0 g/dL (which is rare in ACS), in very severe cases, or if the patient is not getting better after a simple transfusion. This method reduces sickle cells without making the blood too thick. In case Before giving a transfusion to a child with sickle cell disease (SCD), it's best to consult a paediatric haematologist if possible. The benefits of transfusion need to be weighed against risks like blood thickening, iron build-up, and immune reactions. These side effects are uncommon with occasional transfusions but can occur more often in patients who get frequent transfusions (10 or more in a year).^[6]

INHALED NITRIC OXIDE

Inhaled nitric oxide (NO) has been helpful in some sickle cell disease (SCD) patients with acute chest syndrome who also had serious breathing problems like ARDS, low oxygen levels, or high blood pressure in the lungs, and who didn't respond to regular treatments. Inhaled NO works by increasing how well haemoglobin S (Hb S) holds onto oxygen, which may help prevent red blood cells from sickling.^[1]

A small study in children suggested that inhaled NO might help reduce pain and the need for strong pain medicine. However, a larger, more recent study with many patients showed that inhaled NO did not make a big difference in how quickly the pain crisis got better, how long patients stayed in the hospital, how much pain they felt, how much pain medicine they needed, or how often they developed acute chest syndrome compared to those who got a placebo.^[1]

CORTICOSTEROIDES

The use of corticosteroids to treat acute chest syndrome (ACS) in sickle cell disease is controversial. A small study showed that steroids helped mild to moderate ACS get better faster. A short course of dexamethasone therapy may attenuate the course of ACS of sickle cell disease, but it also increases the risk of early readmission after discharge. A retrospective study of 63 patients hospitalized 78 times with ACS over a 2-yr period was reviewed. The clinical course of patients who received prednisone was compared with that of those who did not, particularly to assess the frequency of early (within 2 wk) readmission after discharge. There was no difference in the duration of stay or the need for blood transfusion between the two groups. A short course of prednisone did not significantly increase readmission rate after discharge.^[1]

Strouse and colleagues found that children with asthma and those treated with corticosteroids had a higher risk of being readmitted to the hospital after having acute chest syndrome (ACS). In contrast, blood transfusion seemed to lower that risk. While dexamethasone (a steroid) can shorten how long ACS lasts, it also increases the chance of returning to the hospital for pain, which limits how often it is used.^[1]

Another study by Sobota and colleagues looked at 5,247 hospital stays for ACS between 2004 and 2008 in 32 hospitals. They found that using corticosteroids was linked to longer hospital stays (about 25% longer) and a higher chance of readmission within 3 days. This was true even after adjusting for other factors. Hospitals vary widely in how often they use steroids for ACS, even for patients who also have asthma.^[1]

A clinical trial is conducted the dexamethasone for ACS. Until more results are available from this or other studies, the use of corticosteroids for treating ACS remains uncertain or unclear.^[1]

ANTIBIOTICS

Antibiotics are usually given, although studies by Charache and Davies and others show that they may not make the illness go away faster. There are no studies that clearly compare antibiotics to a placebo or just supportive care. Doctors must choose antibiotics based on the patient's condition, local bacteria types, and test results. Right now, experts suggest using a third or fourth-generation cephalosporin along with a macrolide. However, this should be adjusted depending on local bacteria patterns and lab results from the patient's sputum. Other

options include using a quinolone or a macrolide with a beta-lactam. If the disease gets worse even after transfusions, doctors should check if the antibiotics are working, since there could be gram-negative bacteria or a viral infection.^[1]

HIGH FREQUENCY OSCILLATORY VENTILATION

A small group of cases showed that high-frequency oscillatory ventilation (HFOV) worked well in treating children with severe acute chest syndrome and low oxygen levels.^[1]

ANTIMICROBIAL

Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are needed to find out how safe and effective different antibiotics are for treating ACS. Until more research is available, treatment should include a macrolide to cover atypical bacteria, and also cover *Streptococcus pneumoniae* based on local resistance patterns (ceftriaxone is usually recommended). If Influenza A is suspected or confirmed, it should be treated quickly with oseltamivir.^[6]

Figure 3: Clinical algorithm for acute chest syndrome (ACS) in children with sickle cell disease. Bi Level-PAP: bi-level positive air way pressure; HFNC: high flow nasal cannula oxygen; NIV: non invasive ventilation; NSAID: nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug; SpO₂: oxygen saturation measured by pulse oximetry.

BRONCHOSCOPY

Some investigators suggest regularly using bronchoscopy with BAL to check for fat-filled cells in the lungs to help diagnose bone marrow or fat emboli. However, this test is only helpful in certain cases and should not be used routinely. Bronchoscopy may also help with treatment. One study found that many children had plastic bronchitis with thick mucus plugs, which were removed using the bronchoscope with washing and suction.^[6]

BRONCHODILATORS

Patients with sickle cell disease (SCD) and acute chest syndrome (ACS) often develop wheezing, which suggests narrowed airways, like in asthma. The prevalence of airway hyper-responsiveness is high in children and adults with SCD. Sylvester et al. reported that ACS episodes predispose children to increased air way obstruction. Bronchial hyper-responsiveness may be a component of the acute chest syndrome in patients with SCD. Therefore, bronchodilators may be useful in the treatment for acute chest syndrome. Bronchodilators are given to the patient when wheezing or airflow obstruction is present, and some investigators recommend its routine use in all patients. There is no well designed, adequately powered randomized controlled trial to assess the benefits and risks of the addition of inhaled bronchodilators to established therapies for acute chest syndrome in patients with SCD.^[1]

ARGININE: L-arginine helps make nitric oxide (NO) in the body. In people with sickle cell disease (HbSS), L-arginine levels are already low when they feel normal and drop even more during pain episodes. This lowers the amount of NO in the body and increases stress from harmful molecules.^[1]

Arginase is an enzyme that breaks down L-arginine, and it is higher in people with sickle cell disease (SCD). This reduces the amount of L-arginine available to make nitric oxide (NO). In sickle cell mice, arginine lowers red blood cell density by blocking the Gardos channel. In one study, giving high doses of arginine to 10 patients with pulmonary high blood pressure for 5 days lowered their average lung artery pressure by 15%. However, another study using lower doses of arginine in children for 3 months did not show any changes in arginine levels or lab results. Despite this, a new study is still ongoing to see if arginine can help treat acute chest syndrome.^[1]

ANTICOAGULATION

Researchers have studied on anti-coagulants and antiplatelet drugs in patient with sickle cell disease (SCD). Unfractionated heparin decreases sickle cell adhesion to endothelium under static conditions, as well as P-selecting mediated flow adherence of sickle cells to thrombin-treated human vascular endothelial cells. In a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study of patients with SCD during acute pain episodes, treatment with the low molecular weight heparin, tinzaparin, resulted in a significant reduction in the overall duration of painful crisis, number of days with the most severe pain scores, and duration of hospitalization compared with placebo. The glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitor, eptifibatide, was reported to be safe in a pilot study of HbSS patients, with decreases in platelet aggregation and levels of the inflammatory mediator, soluble CD40 ligand.^[1]

PREVENTION: The best way to prevent ACS is to breathe deeply to keep the small airways in the lungs open (high saturation). If these airways get blocked (small airways are clogged), sickle cells can stick together and cause ACS.^[4]

Here are some simple things your child can do in the hospital or at home to help them breathe more deeply:

- Get out of bed and walk at least 2 or 3 times a day while in the hospital. At home, keep active. People tend to breathe less deeply when lying down or not moving.
- Breathe deeply, even when in pain. When in pain, it is easy to hold your breath or pant without realizing it.
- Use an incentive spirometer in the hospital and home. This device will help your child take slow deep breaths and fill the lungs with air. Using an incentive spirometer is the BEST way to prevent ACS and other complications.^[4]

HEMOGLOBIN F- INDUCING AGENTS

Fetal hemoglobin (Hb F) helps prevent sickle cells from forming by stopping the sickling process. Studies show that higher Hb F levels are linked to milder symptoms in people with sickle cell disease (SCD). A major study called the Multicenter Study of Hydroxyurea (MSH) found that taking hydroxyurea for 2.5 years reduced pain and acute chest syndrome by about half in adults with frequent pain. Higher levels of Hb F are also linked to lower death rates in SCD, so raising Hb F with hydroxyurea may help people live longer. Hydroxyurea may also help by lowering the number of white blood cells called neutrophils.^[1]

Other medicines that can increase fetal hemoglobin (HbF) include DNA demethylating agents, short-chain fatty acids, and histone deacetylase inhibitors. One such drug, decitabine (DNA demethylating agent), has helped raise HbF levels in patients who didn't respond to hydroxyurea. Butyrate, a short-chain fatty acid, also increased HbF in people with sickle cell disease and beta-thalassemia. However, after an early rise, HbF levels dropped again, possibly because butyrate slowed down red blood cell production. More research is needed on these types of drugs for treating sickle cell disease.^[1]

PREVENTION OF HYPOVENTILATION AND ATELECTASIS

Incentive spirometry helps patients take deep breaths and prevent lung collapse (atelectasis). It has been shown to reduce the risk of acute chest syndrome (ACS) by 87% in children with chest or back pain. Because of this, it is recommended for all patients with sickle cell pain crises, and it can also help children who already have ACS. However, some children especially preschoolers or those with severe pain, breathing trouble, or brain issues may not be able to use it. In these cases, another method called positive expiratory pressure (PEP), used with help from a physiotherapist has been found to be noninferior to incentive spirometry in terms of patient satisfaction and length of hospital stay in a small, pilot study of 20 children. The use of noninvasive ventilation (NIV) during sleep, when neither of the above two techniques can be performed, may also improve ventilation and oxygenation and has been found to be safe and well-tolerated in children with vaso-occlusive pain crises.^[6]

CHRONIC BLOOD TRANSFUSION:

Chronic blood transfusion is a helpful treatment to prevent repeated episodes of acute chest syndrome (ACS). A review by Hankins and team found that regular transfusions lower how often ACS happens in people with frequent or severe episodes, but they don't make the episodes less severe. Another study, the Stroke Prevention Trial (STOP), showed that regular transfusions also reduce the number of ACS and pain episodes.^[1]

HEMATOPOIETIC STEM CELL TRANSPLANTATION

The only way to cure for sickle cell disease (SCD) is a stem cell transplant from a donor. However, this treatment (allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation) can have serious side effects and it's hard to find a matching donor. For children who have had several ACS episodes and have a matched **HLA**-sibling donor, a full (myeloablative) stem cell transplant is a good option, with a success rate of over 80%. For adults with a matched sibling donor, a less intense (non-myeloablative) transplant may also be possible.^[1]

CASE REPORT

A 31yrs female patient came to general medicine outpatient department at BMCRC (VIMS), ballari karnataka. Chief complaints of fever and general body ache and myalgia since 2days. And elevated body temperature then patient shifted to emergency for symptomatic treatment. And patient not associated with chills, cough, breathlessness, and no history of vomiting, diarrhea, abdomen pain, chest pain and burning sensation. And patient have no history of comorbidities, asthma, TB, etc.

ON EXAMINATION: BP: 130/70 mm of hg

- BP: 130/70 mm of hg
- Pulse: 92 b/m
- Spo2: 99% at RA
- PICCLE: pallor+ve

ON SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

- CNS: conscious and oriented
- RS: B/L NVBS+ve added sounds
- CVS: S1,S2+ve no added sounds
- P/A: soft non tender no organomegaly

OTHER INVESTIGATIONS

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION	Patient face was dull, slowly speaking and weakness (mayagia) and she was Lower palpaerbal conjunctiva is pale pink which indicates anemia. And pressing nail-beds shows sign of anemia.
LABORATORY TEST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECG • CBC • Serum ferritin • Serum folic acid • LDH • Thyroid profile • HBA1C • Serum electrolyes • LFT • RFT • Peripheral smear • Reticulocyte count • Sputum culture and sensitivity • ABG

PARAMETERS	RESULTS	REFERENCE RANGE
HEMATOLOGY	2/7/25 5/7/25 7/7/25 8/7/25	
HAEMOGLOBIN(Hb)	5.1% 6.4% 9.0% 8.5%	12.5- 16 gm%
TOTAL WBC COUNT	24900 48340 20500 16100	4000- 11000 cells/ cumm
NEUTROPHILS	33 47 50	40- 70%
LYMPHOCYTES	63 47 46	20- 40%
EOSINOPHILS	2 3 2	3- 6%
RBC COUNT	1.68 2.3 2.8 3,12	4.5- 5.5 million/cumm
PLATELET COUNT	5.43 3.4 2.3 2.5	1.5- 4.5 lakh/cumm
PCV	16.5 19.4 29.9 25.8	35- 46%
MCHC	30.9 33.2 30.1 32.7	31-36%
RDW-CV	23.1 21.5 21.1 16.8	11.5- 14.5%
LFT TOTAL PROTIEN	5.5	6- 8.3 g/dl
ALBUMIN	3.1	3.2- 5.4g/dl
GLOBULIN	2.4	2.3- 3g/dl
T.BILIRUBIN	1.9	0.2- 1.2 mg/dl
BIL.CONJUGATE	0.8	0.1- 0.4 mg/dl
BIL. UNCONJUGATE	1.1	0.2- 0.7mg/dl
AST/SGOT	53 U/L	0-45U/L
ALP	363 U/L	20- 140 U/L
S. FERRITIN	>2000	11- 307ng/ml
S. FOLIC ACID	13.25	2.5-20ng/ml
LDH	2010	225- 450IU/ L
HBA1C	3.6	
MBG	57	<6
THYROID PROFILE FT4 (FREET4)	1.7 ng/dl	0.92- 1.68ng/ dl
PERIPHERAL SMEAR	Haemolytic blood picture dimorphic anemia with marked anisocytosis with presence of sickle and numeric.	
SPUTUM C/S	Gram stain: 6-8 pus cells/ LPF epithelial cells/ LPF seen occasional gram positive cocci in pairs seen. CULTURE REPORT: commensals isolated, kindly correlated clinically.	
USG ABDOMEN AND PELVIS	Hepatomegaly cholelithiasis	
ABG REPORT		
PH	7.45	7.35- 7.45
pCO2	38	35- 45mmHg
pO2	105	75- 100mmHg
HCO3	25.5	22- 26mEq/L
Sat.O2	98%	>95%

Figure 4: This Figure Showing Abnormality In Abdomen Pelvic And Chest X Ray.

PHARMACOLOGICAL THERAPY

SL.NO	NAME OF THE DRUG	FREQUENCY	ROUTE	DOSE	DAYS
1.	INJ- CEFTRIAZONE	1-0-1	IV	1gm	1-5D
2.	INJ- PANTOPRAZOLE	1-0-0	IV	40mg	1-12D
3.	INJ- ONDONSETRON	1-1-1	IV	4mg	1-12D
4.	INJ- PARACETAMOL	SOS	IV	1gm	1-12D
5.	TAB- PARACETAMOL	1-1-1-1	PO	500mg	1-12D
6.	INJ- TRAMADOL	1-1-1	IV	50mg in 100ml ns	1-12d
7.	1 pint RBC				On 2D and 4thD-6thD
8.	INJ- PIPZO	1-1-1	IV	4.5gm	On 5D-11 TH D
9.	SYP: Lactulose	1-1-0	PO	10ml	ON SD 12 TH D

DISCHARGE MEDICATIONS

SL.NO	NAME OF THE DRUG	FREQUENCY	ROUTE	DOSE
1.	TAB- IRONE FOLIC ACID	1-0-1	PO	333mg
2.	TAB- FOLIC ACID	1-0-1	PO	5mg
3.	TAB- MULTIVITAMIN B COMPLEX	0-1-0	PO	
4.	SYP- MULTIVITAMIN	1-0-1	PO	5ml

DISCUSSION

Acute Chest Syndrome (ACS) is a life-threatening pulmonary complication and a leading cause of hospitalization and mortality in patients with sickle cell disease (SCD). It is characterized by new pulmonary infiltrates on imaging alongside clinical features such as fever, chest pain, cough, dyspnea, and respiratory distress. However, the ACS is complex and multifactorial pathogenesis, which may include infection, fat embolism and hypoventilation. Early recognition and prompt symptomatic treatment of ACS are critical to reducing morbidity and mortality.

In this case, a 31-year-old female presented with fever, generalized body aches, and myalgia of two days' duration. Although initially not associated with typical respiratory symptoms such as cough or breathlessness, the patient developed signs suggestive of systemic inflammation and underlying anemia as evidenced by pallor and pressing nail-beds. On clinical examination, her vital parameters were within normal limits, and oxygen saturation was maintained at 99% at room atmosphere. However, laboratory investigations were indicative of hemolysis, anemia, and a systemic inflammatory response.

Hematology findings showed reduced hemoglobin, RBC count, and neutrophils, with elevated total leukocyte and platelet counts. Where in Liver function tests elevated bilirubin, ALP, and AST levels, and the total protein and albumin reduced suggesting hepatocellular

involvement likely secondary to hemolysis and cholelithiasis—both common complications in SCD. The peripheral smear confirmed a hemolytic blood picture with dimorphic anemia, marked anisocytosis, and the presence of sickled red cells, further confirming the underlying diagnosis of sickle cell disease.

Sputum culture revealed occasional gram-positive cocci, and the chest X-ray showed bilateral pneumonia, which, in the context of SCD, is strongly suggestive of ACS. In thyroid profile slightly elevated FT4 and Ultrasonography revealed hepatomegaly and cholelithiasis.

Management focused on supportive care including oxygen therapy to maintain saturations above 96%, analgesics and antipyretics such as paracetamol and pain killer such as tramadol and antiemetics (ondansetron) for nausea and vomiting. Proton pump inhibitors such as pantoprazole were administered to prevent gastrointestinal irritation, especially due to analgesics. Empirical broad-spectrum antibiotics like piperacillin-tazobactam (Pipzo) were initiated to manage suspected bacterial. In addition; syrup lactulose was given to support liver function. The patient received blood transfusions due to evidence of severe anemia, and her condition improved steadily with normalization of laboratory parameters during the hospital stay.

In cases of severe or recurrent ACS, advanced therapies such as high-frequency oscillatory ventilation, chronic transfusion therapy, or even hematopoietic stem cell transplantation may be necessary. Preventive measures, including incentive spirometry, exchange transfusions, and emerging therapeutic agents such as nitric oxide donors, L-arginine, and bronchodilators, have shown potential in reducing morbidity and recurrence rates. However, further research is required to establish the efficacy of these novel treatments and to optimize standardized treatment protocols for ACS in patients with SCD.

This case highlights the importance of early recognition of ACS—even in the absence of classic respiratory symptoms—and the need for a multidisciplinary approach in managing the systemic complications of sickle cell disease. Timely intervention with appropriate supportive and targeted therapies can significantly improve patient outcomes and reduce the risk of mortality.

CONCLUSION

Acute Chest Syndrome (ACS) remains a life-threatening complication in patients with sickle cell disease (SCD), often presenting with nonspecific or atypical symptoms. This case underscores the importance of early recognition and prompt intervention, even in the absence of initial respiratory manifestations. The patient exhibited classical signs of hemolysis, anemia, and systemic inflammation, with subsequent imaging and laboratory findings confirming ACS. Effective management such as supportive care, blood transfusion, and empiric antimicrobial therapy—resulted in clinical improvement and stabilization. This case also highlights the need for comprehensive, multidisciplinary care, given the multisystem involvement seen in SCD. Preventive strategies and emerging adjunctive therapies such as nitric oxide donors and L-arginine show potential but require further validation through clinical research. Ultimately, timely diagnosis, aggressive supportive management, and individualized treatment plans are crucial in improving outcomes and reducing ACS-associated morbidity and mortality in SCD patients.

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REFERENCE

1. Paul RN, Castro OL, Aggarwal A, Oneal PA. Acute chest syndrome: sickle cell disease. *European journal of haematology*, 2011 Sep; 87(3): 191-207.
2. <https://nssg.oxford-haematology.org.uk/red-cell/documents/acute-management-sickle-cell-disease/S10-acute-chest-syndrome-in-scd.pdf>
3. <https://www.rcpath.org/resourceLibrary/audittembcshaem38.html>
4. <https://www.nationwidechildrens.org/-/media/nch/family-resources/helping-hands/documents/hhi225.pdf>
5. Gladwin MT, Schechter AN, Shelhamer JH, Ognibene FP. The acute chest syndrome in sickle cell disease: possible role of nitric oxide in its pathophysiology and treatment. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*, 1999 May 1; 159(5): 1368-76.
6. Ahmed B, Arigliani M, Gupta A. Respiratory management of acute chest syndrome in children with sickle cell disease. *European Respiratory Review*, 2024 Sep 18; 33(173).